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Application of Phase Transfer Catalysis in the Synthesis of Flavonoids. Part-I : Alkylation of Some Phenols**

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A new technique, commonly referred to as phase transfer catalysis or extractive alkylation, has come into prominence in recent years. Its application has been pioneered by the research groups of Makosza, Brandstrom and Stark^{1,2}. This new technique has been applied in various fields of organic synthesis.

In connection with the synthesis of flavonoids, we become interested in applying the phase transfer catalysis technique on the alkylation of various phenols, phenolic aldehydes, hydroxyacetophenones and phenolic acids which are common starting materials in this area of synthesis. Moreover, the flavonoids so far reported from plant sources are derived mainly from pyrogallol, resorcinol, phloroglucinol and different phenolic aldehydes or acids. Methylation and benzylation of phenolic hydroxyl groups are common procedures in the synthesis of flavonoids. In view of these, we undertook the studies on the alkylation of various phenols by using phase transfer catalysis technique. The results of this study are the subject matter of the present communication.

Recently, McKillop *et al*³ have reported a simple, rapid and efficient procedure for the monoalkylation of both simple and highly hindered phenols by using phase transfer catalysis technique. In

majority of the cases they obtained higher yields as compared to the classical methods.

McKillop's work³ in this area is mainly confined in the monoalkylation of phenols. Since the present study is related with flavonoid synthesis, so our main approach in this study is the polyalkylation of different phenols. The compounds selected for alkylation are essential starting materials for the synthesis of flavonoids. The results of such polyalkylation are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—o-ALKYLATION OF POLYHYDROXYPHENOLS AND PHENOLIC ALDEHYDES*

Compound	Alkylating agent	Yield %
1. Pyrogallol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
	PhCH ₂ Cl	40
2. Phloroglucinol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
3. Resorcinol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
4. Pyrocatechol	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
5. Vanillin	PhCH ₂ Cl	70
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
6. o-Vanillin	PhCH ₂ Cl	45
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
7. 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	75
	PhCH ₂ Cl	40

* All the alkylated products gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

TABLE 2—o-ALKYLATION OF POLYHYDROXYACETOPHENONES AND PHENOLIC ACIDS*

Compound	Alkylating agent	Yield %
1. 2,4-Dihydroxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	PhCH ₂ Cl	40
2. 2-Hydroxy-4-benzoyloxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
3. 2,4,6-Trihydroxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	90
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
4. 2,3,4-Trihydroxyacetophenone	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
5. Gallic acid	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
6. 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	PhCH ₂ Cl	70
7. Methyl ester of syringic acid	(CH ₃) ₂ SO ₄	80
	PhCH ₂ Cl	70

* All the alkylated products gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

It is evident from the present study that the yields of methylated products are extremely high in comparison to the conventional procedure. In case of benzylation, the yields of the product are comparable to the conventional methods but the benzylation product prepared by the phase transfer technique required less time and easy work-up procedure. So, the application of phase transfer catalysis technique on the polyalkylation of phenols could overcome the different drawbacks of the conventional alkylation methods and alkylation could be done more suitably. Further work in this area is in progress.

Experimental

The following general procedure have been followed.

(i) *Monoalkylation*: A method similar to the one cited in literature³ has been followed.

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(ii) *Polyalkylation*: A mixture of phenol (10 mmoles), sodium hydroxide (15 mmoles for each hydroxyl group), alkylating agent (15 mmoles for each hydroxyl group) and quaternary ammonium bromide (0.1-0.5 mmole) in water (50 ml) and chloroform (50 ml) as an organic solvent was stirred at room temp. for 0.5-4 hr. The product was isolated following the same work-up procedure as in the case of monoalkylations.

(iii) *Benzylation*: The reaction is carried out at boiling water bath temp. in CH_2Cl_2 as organic solvent.

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was used as catalyst in all the cases.

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Studies in Fluorinated 1,3-Diketones and Related Compounds. Part-XVI: Studies in Lanthanide 1,3-Diketonates as NMR Shift Reagents

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FLUORINATED 1,3-diketones and related compounds are indispensable reagents in analytical chemistry and some of the most recent uses are in analysing lunar samples¹, cobalt in vitamin B₁₂ and in detection of other trace elements in blood, serum and other essential biological materials. In 1969, Hinckley² discovered that the addition of bis-pyridine adduct of *tris*-dipivalomethanatoeuropium produced downfield shift in cholesterol. Since then, the paramagnetic lanthanide(III) 1,3-diketonates are used as nmr shift reagents and the fluorinated 1,3-diketonates act as superior nmr shift reagents due to their stronger interaction with nucleophiles, (viz., ethers, ketones, alcohols, esters and amines). This is most likely due to the increased acidity of the fluorinated chelates and decrease in the basicity of fluorinated 1,3-diketones and increased solubility. Recently, we have undertaken a comprehensive programme to develop the chemistry of fluorinated 1,3-diketones³ and related compounds⁴ and as a part of this, we reported the synthesis of some new fluorinated lanthanide 1,3-diketonates⁵. We now report

their ability to act as nmr shift reagents with particular reference to shifts produced in *n*-hexanol and *p*-fluoroaniline. The following compounds synthesized earlier by us⁶ have been examined as nmr shift reagents.

1. [4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III).
2. [4,4,5,5,6,6,6-Heptafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-hexanedionato]praseodymium(III).
3. [4,4,5,5,5-Pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]samarium(III).

Experimental

The appropriate lanthanide chloride (0.004 mole), dissolved in a minimum amount of methanol, was added very slowly to the methanolic solution of 1, 3-diketonato enolate anion (0.012 mole) (generated by dissolving the corresponding 1,3-diketone in methanol and then adding 2% methanolic sodium hydroxide solution). The lanthanide 1,3-diketonate was precipitated by slow addition of a ten fold excess of water to the resulting methanolic solution. The precipitated lanthanide 1,3-diketonates were crystallized from dichloromethane or benzene. Finally, they were dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide for 24 hr.

General procedure for observing shifts: In a clean and dry nmr sample tube, was taken a definite amount of lanthanide 1,3-diketonate, which had been dried in a drying pistol. CDCl_3 was then added to it followed by definite number of drops of alcohol or amine. NMR spectra were taken after a regular interval of time, viz., 1, 2, 3, 4, 24 hr. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of the data observed, it is presumed that interaction of nucleophile with lanthanide 1,3-diketonates is pseudocontact in nature. In the course of time, the coordination angle of nucleophile with lanthanide 1,3-diketonates changes and as a result, a reversal of shifts produced has been noticed. It is well known that pseudocontact interaction is governed by McConnell and Robertson equation.

$$\Delta\delta = \frac{X3\cos^2\theta - 1}{r^3}$$

where r = nucleus-metal distance vector.

θ = the angle between this vector and the principal symmetry axis.

X = constant for a given metal adduct at a given temperature.

It predicts that if coordination angle is greater than 54.7°, a reversal of normal shifts is observed. The results are recorded in the Table 1.

In general, upfield shifts were produced by [4,4,5,5,5-pentafluoro-1-(4'-fluorophenyl)-1,3-pentanedionato]praseodymium(III) with *n*-hexanol. Shift